
**Use and awareness of INFLIBNET N-List
e-resources among Faculty Members of
Government Degree Colleges Affiliated to Sri
Venkateswara University, Tirupati, A.P.**

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Abstract

The study investigates the awareness, usage, and access patterns of N-LIST e-resources among faculty at Government Degree Colleges affiliated with Sri Venkateswara University, Tirupati. It aims to assess awareness, frequency of use, types of e-resources consulted, and challenges faced. Data were collected from 290 faculty members using a questionnaire, revealing moderate awareness and use of N-LIST services, with occasional use primarily through college libraries. Identified barriers include slow internet, difficulty in locating relevant information, and insufficient training. The study calls for continuous user education, improved ICT infrastructure, and effective awareness strategies to enhance N-LIST resource utilization, providing insights for librarians, administrators, and policymakers to improve digital resource management and support services.

Keywords

N-LIST Services; Government degree colleges;
E-journals & E-books; S.V. University,

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1. Introduction

Academic libraries' main objective is to collect, organize, and disseminate information to users based on their requirements. The use of information and communication technologies (ICT) has made traditional libraries more modern during the last few decades. Electronic resources, including e-books and e-journals, have become the largest and fastest-growing category within library collections. The majority of academic libraries now include these electronic resources as normal and essential part of their collections.

The Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD), now the Ministry of Education (MoE), launched the N-LIST (National Library and Information Services Infrastructure for Scholarly Content) program in response to the high cost of e-journals and the challenges of managing electronic resources. The INDEST-AICTE Consortium, IIT Delhi, and the e-Shodsindhu Consortium, INFLIBNET Centre, are working together on this project. Through a server set up at the INFLIBNET Centre, the program gives recipient institutions access to a selection of e-resources, allowing college staff, researchers, and students to access intellectual content. The current study intends to investigate the awareness and utilisation status of faculty members of Government Degree Colleges affiliated to Sri Venkateswara University area's awareness and utilisation of e-journals and e-books made available through the N-LIST initiative.

1.1 Status of access to the N-List programme in Andhra Pradesh:

As of January 2026, 281 government, aided, and private colleges in Andhra Pradesh are registered under the N-LIST programme, but only 179 have activated access to e-resources. In the S.V. University-affiliated region, out of 21 registered government and private colleges, only 7 government colleges and 1 private college have enabled N-LIST e-resource access, indicating underutilization of the programme.

2. Review of Literature

An Investigation into the accessibility and user awareness of N-List e-resources was conducted by Goutham & Gulati (2025)⁴. Their study examines the knowledge of and access to electronic materials

available through the N-List service among instructors and students at a few Lucknow-affiliated colleges. Das & Singh (2024)⁹ used beneficiary relationship analysis to analyse the N-List Project's implementation in the state of Assam and compare it with the national status. Beneficiary relationship factor analysis and its influence are essential for evaluating project efficiency.

Battacharyya & Chatterjee (2023)² investigated how the faculty and students at Vivekananda Mahavidyalaya, Haripal, Hooghly, used and were aware of N-List resources. The study emphasises how Vivekananda Mahavidyalaya users are using and aware of the N-List application. Vinay & Baby (2023)⁸ investigated the use and knowledge of N-List journals and periodicals within the Tribal region's intellectual community. With specific reference to Shaheed Bhima Nayak (SNB) Govt. PG College, Badwani, Their Study's primary goal is to investigate the usefulness and awareness of N-List Databases (E-Books, Journals, etc.) among the intellectual community of tribal regions. They conducted research to understand perceptions of N-List e-resources' usability and awareness.

Das, Rumi (2022)³ investigated the use and understanding of the N-List e-resources consortium among the academic members of the THB college library in Sonitpur, Assam. The goal of this study is to determine the N-List consortium's utilisation statistics, faculty members' awareness of the consortium, the reasons for utilising it, and the degree of pleasure experienced while using these services.

Mamatha (2022)⁵ researched how the teachers and students at Government's First Grade College in the Chikkamangalur District used e-resources (N-List). Her study shows that teachers and students are aware of the INFLIBNET centre's N-List programme, the reasons for using e-resources, how to link patterns of e-resources, and the issues they faced while using these services in the library.

N-List is a useful e-resource for academic study and advancement, according to Pradan (2022)⁷. The author specifically addressed the INFLIBNET N-List project, its elements, e-resource availability, access and retrieval, membership process, current state, and colleges' responsibilities in research and development.

The goal of Bansode & Jadhar (2021)¹ is to determine whether faculty members of a certain college connected to Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune, are aware of and utilize the N-List consortium. Panda (2021)⁶ studied the understanding and use of N-List e-resources among postgraduate students from Punjab's government-aided colleges, including their purpose, degree of satisfaction, and challenges encountered when using them.

3. Objectives of the study

- To know the awareness of N-List e-resource services among the faculty members of Selected Government Degree College libraries affiliated to Sri Venkateswara University, Tirupati;
- To study the availability of e-resources in Government Degree college libraries,
- To know the level of use of the N-List e-resource services among the faculty members;
 - To know the purpose of using N-List services;
- To comprehend the high accessibility of full-text e-books and e-journals among the various types of materials in the N-List program;
- To find the quality and problems while accessing N-List services.

3.1 Scope and limitation of the study

The scope of the study was restricted to 7 Degree Government & Autonomous colleges with a subscription to N-LIST, located in Tirupati District and affiliated to Sri Venkateswara University, Tirupati.

3. Methodology

A survey method was adopted to collect the data. Seven government degree colleges affiliated with Sri Venkateswara University in Tirupati district and participating in the N-LIST programme were selected for the study. Stratified sampling was used for data collection, and questionnaires were distributed to 50% of the members of the total population in each college. Details of the population are presented in Table 1. A total of 145 questionnaires were distributed among the total 290 faculty members. The data collected through the questionnaire has been analysed and presented in tabular form using MS-Excel.

Table 1: DEGREE COLLEGES

S. No.	Name of the College	Place	Total members	Number of questionnaires
1.	Government Degree college	Nagari	30	15
2.	Government degree college	Kuppam	34	17
3.	Government degree college	Puttur	66	33
4.	Government Degree college	Madanapalli	30	15
5.	Sri Vidyaprakasa Ananda Government Degree College for Men	Sri Kalahstri	30	15
6.	Subharam Govt. Degree College	Punganuru	15	8
7.	Sri Padmavati Women's Degree & PG College	Tirupati.	85	42
Total			290	145

5. Analysis

All the collected Data was analysed based on the percentages calculations. Interpretation of the data is also presented along with conclusion.

5.1 Gender

A question has been asked to the respondents to know the gender in faculty of selected Government Degree Colleges in Tirupati District. The replies given by them are shown in the table-1

Table – 1 Gender

S. I	Gender	Responses	(%)
1	Male	87	64.44
2	Female	48	35.55
Total	Total	135	100%

It is observed from the above table and figure shows that male respondents are 64.44% and female respondents are 35.55% from Government Degree College affiliated to Sri Venkateswara Univerisyt, Tirupati District.

It can be concluded that highest number of the respondents (64.44%) are male and (35.55%) are female respondents.

5.2. Separate building for Library

A question has been asked to know about the library building. The replies given by them are shown in the table-2.

Table 2: Separate building for library

Sl. No	Building for library	Responses	(%)
1	Yes	137	94.4
2	No	8	5.5
Total	Total	145	100%

It is depicted from the above table that most of the respondents (94.4%) replied YES, and (5.5%) of the respondents replied NO regarding a separate library building. It can be concluded that most respondents (94.4%) answered YES to having a separate library building.

5.3 Library Visit

A Question has been asked of the respondents to know about their library visits. The replies given by respondents are shown in Table 3

Table 3: Library visit

Sl. No.	Library Visit	Responses	(%)
1	Yes	125	92.60
2	No	10	7.40
Total	Total	135	100%

Table 3 shows that most of the respondents (92.60%) replied YES, they are visiting the library, and the remaining of the respondents (7.40%) replied No, they are not visiting the library.

It can be concluded that most of the respondents (93.3%) are visiting the library frequently.

Figure-2 Library Visit

5.4 . Available e-resources

Respondents have been asked about the availability of e-resources. The replies given by the respondents are shown in Table 4

Table 4: Available e-resources

SNo.	Available e-resources	Responses	(%)
1	E-books	105	77.77
2	E-journals	102	75.55
3	Full text documents/journal aggregators	55	40.74
4	Bibliographic Databases	45	33.33
5	OPACs	40	29.62
6	Indexing and abstracting journals	40	29.62
7	CD-ROM databases	32	23.70
8	Thesis/dissertations	25	18.51

(Respondents are allowed to answer more than one)

Respondents are allowed to answer more than one option. It is evident from the above table that majority of the respondents' (77.77%) were available e-resource is E-books, followed by E-Journals (75.55%), Full test documents/journals aggregators 40.74(%), Bibliographic Databases (33.33%), OPACs and Indexing and abstracting journals (29.62%), CD-ROM databases (23.70%) and Thesis/dissertations (18.51%).

It can be concluded that the majority of the respondents' (77.77%) available e-resources are e-books from the N-List service provided by their libraries.

Figure 3: Available e-resources

5.5 Aware on N-List services

Respondents were asked about their awareness of N-List services. The replies given by respondents are shown in Table 5

Table 5 Aware on N-List services

Sl. No	Aware on N-List services	Responses	(%)
1	Yes	135	93.10
2	No	10	6.89
Total	Total	145	99.99

The above table shows that most respondents (93.10%) were aware of N-List services, while the remaining (6.89%) were not. It is concluded that most of the respondents (90%) of the faculty have awareness of N-List services.

*Of the 145 respondents, 10 are not aware of N-List. Therefore, only 135 questions were considered for further analysis.

5.6 Place of access of N-List services

Respondents were asked about their access to N-List services. The replies given by the respondents are shown in the table – 6

Table 6: Place of access of N-List services

Sl. No.	Place of access to N-List services	Responses	(%)
1	College library	114	84.44
2	Home	46	34.07
3	Department	35	25.92
4	Internet cafe	10	7.40

(Respondents are allowed to answer more than one)

Here, respondents may select more than one option. It is evident from the above table that the majority of the respondents (84.44%) were accessing N-List services at the College library, followed by Home (34.07%), Department (25.92%) and Internet café (7.40).

It can be concluded that the majority of respondents (84.44%) accessed N-List services at their college libraries to obtain the information they needed.

5.7. Frequency of accessing N-List services

Respondents have been asked about their frequency of accessing N-List services. The replies given by them are shown in Table – 7

Table 7: Frequency of accessing N-List services

Sl. No	Frequency	Responses	(%)
1	Occasionally	50	37.04
2	Twice in a week	40	29.63
3	Daily	35	25.93
4	Fortnight	10	7.40
Total	Total	135	100

It is observed from the above table that the highest percentage of respondents (37.04%) accessed N-List services occasionally, followed by twice a week (29.63%), Daily (25.93%), and fortnightly (7.40%).

It can be concluded that the highest percentage of respondents (41.37%) access N-List services occasionally in their college libraries.

5.8 Approach point in N-List service

Respondents have been asked about their approach to finding information in N-List services. Their replies are shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Approach point in N-List service

Sl. No	Approach	Responses	(%)
1	Subject	85	62.96
2	Title	60	44.44
3	Key words	46	34.07
4	Author	40	29.62

(Respondents are allowed to answer more than one)

Respondents are allowed to answer more than one option. It is evident that more than half of the respondents (62.96%) approached the subject, followed by Title (44.44%), Keywords (34.07%), and Author (29.62%).

It can be concluded that more than half of the respondents (62.96%) are approaching the point where the subject is the main focus, and 29.62% are approaching the point where the author is the main focus to obtain the required information from N-list services in their college libraries.

5.9. Journal access for full text in N-List services

Respondents have been asked about the journal access to full text via N-List services. Their replies are shown in Table 9.

Table 9: Journal access for full text in N-List services

Sl. No	Full text access	Responses	(%)
3	Indian Journals	95	70.37
5	JUSTOR	30	22.22
4	Institute of Physics	25	18.51
1	American Institute of Physic	20	14.81
2	Annual Review	20	14.81
6	Oxford University Press	20	14.81
7	Royal Society of Chemistry	20	14.81
8	HW Wilson	5	3.70

(Respondents are allowed to answer more than one)

Respondents are allowed to answer more than one option. It is evident from the above table that highest percentage of the respondents (70.37%) were accessing full text from the Indian Journals, followed by JUSTOR (22.22%), Institute of Physics (18.51%), American Institute of Physics, Annual Review, Oxford University Press, and Royal Society of Chemistry (14.81%), and HW Wilson (3.70),

It can be concluded that the highest percentage of respondents (70.37%) access full-text information from the Indian Journal via N-List services at their college libraries.

5.10. E-books provide full text from N-List services

Respondents were asked to identify the e-books they access to obtain full-text information from N-List services. The replies given by them are shown in Table 10.

Table – 10 E-books access full text from N-List services

Sl. No.	e-book access for full text	Responses	(%)
1	E-Library	85	62.96
2	Spring e Books	50	37.03
3	Sage Publication e Books	25	18.52
4	Taylor & Francis e Books	25	18.52
5	Cambridge Books online	20	14.81
6	EBSCO Host-Net Library	20	14.81
7	Oxford Scholarship Online	20	14.81
8	My-library McGraw Hill	20	14.81
9	Hindustan Book Agency	15	11.11
10	Institute of South East Asian Studies (ISEAS) Books	15	11.11
11	South Asian Achieves (Through NDL)	5	3.70
12	World E-Library	5	3.70
13	South Asia	0	0.0

(Respondents are allowed to answer more than one)

Respondents are permitted to select more than one choice in this table. The above table shows that over half of the respondents (62.96%) were using e-books to access full text information from E-Library, followed by Spring e-books (37.03%), Sage Publications e-books and Taylor & Francis e-books (18.52%), Cambridge Books online, Oxford Scholarship online, My-Library McGraw Hill, and EBSCO Host-Net Library (14.81%), Hindustan Book Agency and Institute of South East Asian Studies (ISEAS) Nooks (11.11%), South Asian Achieves (Through NDL) and Wold E-Library (3.70%) and South Asia (0.0%).

It can be concluded that the highest percentage of the respondents (62.96%) are accessing full-text information from the E-library, and South Asia (0.0%) from the N-List services.

5.11 Purpose of using N-List services

Respondents were asked about the purpose of using N-List services. The replies given by them are shown in the table - 11

Table 11: Purpose of using N-List services

Sl. No	Purpose	Responses	(%)
1	To know latest developments in the	70	51.85

	subject		
2	Reading/Writing research	55	40.74
3	To read Journal articles pertaining to subject	55	40.74
4	To prepare projects/dissertation/Theses	40	29.62
5	To prepare for seminars, Conferences, and workshops	35	25.92
6	To prepare assignments	30	22.22

(Respondents are allowed to answer more than one)

Respondents are permitted to select more than one option. It is depicted that over half of the respondents (51.85%) were using N-List to know latest developments in the subject, followed by Reading/Writing research and to read Journal articles pertaining to subject (40.74%), To prepare projects/dissertation/Theses (29.62%), To prepare for seminars, Conferences, and workshops (25.92%) and To prepare assignments (22.22%).

It can be concluded that over half of the respondents (51.85%) use N-List to stay up to date on the subject, and 20.68% use N-List services to prepare assignments.

5.12 Quality of N-List services

Respondents have been asked about the quality of N-List services. Their replies are shown in Table 12.

Table –12 Quality of N-List services

Sl. No.	Quality	Responses	(%)
1	Excellent	56	41.49
2	Very Good	35	25.93
3	Good	32	23.70
4	Average	6	4.44
5	Not Useful	6	4.44
Total	Total	135	100

It is evident from the above table that the highest percentage of the respondents (41.49%) replied that the Quality of N-List is excellent, followed by Very Good (25.93%), Good (23.70%), and finally Average and Not Useful (4.44%). It can be concluded that the highest percentage of respondents (41.49%) are pleased with the quality of N-List services, and 4.44% replied that the quality was average and found

N-List services not useful in their respective college libraries.

Figure 4 Quality of N-List services

5.13. Assistance from the staff

A question has been posed to the respondents; to know staff assistance in N-List services in the library. The replies given by them are shown in the table – 15

Table 15 Assistance from the staff

Sl. No.	Staff assistance	Responses	(%)
1	Yes	115	85.19
2	No	20	14.81
Total	Total	135	100

Table 15 shows that the majority of respondents (85.19%) seek assistance from staff, while the remaining (14.81%) do not.

It can be concluded that 85.19% of the respondents replied positively, indicating that they are seeking assistance from library staff to access N-List.

5.14. Need a training/Awareness programme on N-List services

Respondents have been asked about the need for a training/awareness programme on N-List services. Their replies are shown in Table 14.

Table 14 Need Training/Awareness programme on N-List services

Sl. No.	Need of Training/Awareness Programme	Responses	%
1	Strongly agreed	70	51.86
2	Agreed	50	37.03
4	No any opinion	10	7.40
3	Not Agreed	5	3.70
Total	Total	135	99.99

The table shows that over half of the respondents (51.86%) strongly agreed that there should be a

training/awareness programme on N-List services, followed by agreed (37.03%), no opinion (7.40%), and not agreed (3.70%).

It can be concluded that over half of the respondents (51.86) strongly agreed that there should be a training/awareness programme on N-List services in their college libraries.

5.15. Preferred external storage

Respondents have been asked to indicate their preferred external storage device for storing information from N-List services. Their replies are shown in Table 15.

Table 15: Preferred external storage

Sl. No.	Preferred external storage	Responses	%
1	CD-ROM	25	18.51
2	Pen drive	71	52.60
3	Portable hard disk	9	6.67
4	Memory Card	25	18.51
5	Blue-ray Disk	5	3.70
Total	Total	135	99.99

As depicted in the above table, the highest percentage of respondents (52.51%) preferred a pen drive for external storage, followed by CD-ROM and Memory Card (18.51%), Portable hard disk (6.67%), and Blu-ray disk (3.70%) for external storage.

It can be concluded that more than half of the respondents (52.51%) prefer a pen drive for external storage from N-List services in their college library, and a Blu-ray disk (3.44%) for external storage.

5.16. Facing problems while accessing N-List Services

Respondents were asked about the problems they face when accessing N-List services. The replies given by them are shown in the table below – 16.

Table 16: Facing problems while accessing N-List Services

Sl. No.	Facing problems	Responses	(%)
1	Difficulty in finding relevant information	70	51.87
2	Much time taken to view/download pages	55	40.74
3	Limited number of	35	25.92

	computers		
4	Overload of information on the internet	25	18.51
5	Lack of assistance by library staff	15	11.11

(Respondents are allowed to answer more than one)

Respondents are permitted to select more than one choice in this table. It is observed from the above table that more than half of the respondents' (51.87%) were facing problems while finding relevant information, followed by much Time taking to view/download pages (40.74%), a limited number of computers (25.92%), Overload of information on the internet (18.51%), and Lack of assistance by library staff (11.11%).

It can be concluded that over half of the respondents (51.87%) are having problems accessing relevant information while using the library's N-List services.

5.17 Effect of N-List services for your research projects

Respondents have been asked to assess the impact of N-List services on their research projects. The replies given by them are shown in the table below – 17

Table 17: Effect of N-List services for your research projects

Sl. No.	Effect of N-List services	Responses	(%)
1	Non	70	51.87
2	Improved	25	18.51
3	Highly improved	20	14.81
4	Moderately improved	15	11.11
5	No effect	5	3.70
Total	Total	135	100

It is evident from the above table that more than half of the respondents (51.87%) replied not in any research project, followed by Improved (18.51), Highly improved (14.81), Moderately improved (11.11%), and No effect (3.70%) of N-List Services for their research project.

It can be concluded that more than half of the respondents (51.87%) reported not being involved in any research projects, and that no effect (3.44%) of N-List Services on their research projects.

6. Findings

- The highest number of respondents (64.44%) are male, and (35.55%) are female.
- Most respondents (93.3%) visit the library frequently.
- Most respondents (90.3%) are aware of e-resources.
- The majority of the respondents' (77.77%) available e-resource is E-books from the N-List service providing by their libraries.
- Most of the respondents (90%) of the faculty are aware of N-List services, and 10% of them are not aware of N-List services.
- The majority of respondents (84.44%) accessed N-List services at their college libraries to obtain the information they needed.
- The highest percentage of respondents (41.37%) access N-List services occasionally in their college library, and 7.40% access Fortnight.
- Half of the respondents (62.96%) are approaching the point, and 29.62% of the respondents are approaching the author point
- The highest percentage of the respondents (70.37%) are accessing full-text information from the Indian Journal in N-List services at their college libraries.
- The highest percentage of respondents (62.96%) is accessing full-text information from the E-library, and South Asia (0.0%) from the N-List services.
- Over half of the respondents (51.85%) use N-List to stay up to date on the latest developments in the subject, and 20.68% use N-List services to prepare assignments.
- The majority of respondents (85.19%) responded positively, stating that they are seeking assistance from library staff to access N-List.
- The highest percentage of respondents (41.49%) are pleased with the quality of N-List service, and 4.44% replied that the service is average and found it not useful in their respective college libraries.
- Over half of the respondents (51.86) strongly agreed that there should be a training/awareness programme on N-List services.
- More than half of the respondents (52.51%) prefer a pen drive for external storage from N-List services in their college library, and a Blu-ray disk (3.44%) for external storage.
- Over half of the respondents (51.87%) are having problems while accessing relevant information using the library's N-List services in their college library.

- More than half of the respondents (51.87%) reported not being involved in any research projects.

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